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DUOX2 silencing is a feature of metastasis to the liver in human cancer.

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The liver is the most common site of metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer (1-5). We describe differentially expressed and silencing of DUOX2 in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer and in humans with breast cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the liver, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to describe the liver metastasis transcriptome.

Results

Figure 1: DUOX2 is differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

I. Liver metastasis and primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=4 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer
n=3 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
50506	9.41E-06	1.107	4.4302764	4.9029592	1630.63	DUOX2	483/19486	97.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the colorectum and in liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer, we discovered differential expression of dual oxidase 2, encoded by *DUOX2* in metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *DUOX2* changed more than 95% of the human colorectal cancer (CRC) liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,486 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of *DUOX2* messenger RNA in CRC liver metastases, demonstrating down-regulation of *DUOX2* during disease progression in colorectal cancer.

II. Liver metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer.

n=10 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer
n=10 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
50506	2.36E-06	0.853	4.7201408	4.02612976	469.73	DUOX2	35/15341	99.8

Through measurement of total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, we validated differential expression of *DUOX2* in human colorectal cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of *DUOX2* here changed more than 99% of the liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 15,341 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of *DUOX2* messenger RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating down-regulation of *DUOX2* during disease progression and metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

1 III. Liver metastasis in patients with breast cancer.

2 GSE124647

3 *n*=19 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

4 *n*=16 liver metastasis from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
219727_at	3.99E-02	2.130509	-4.1833	0.7441717		DUOX2	1131/22283	

7 DUOX2 silencing was also a transcriptional feature of liver metastasis in breast cancer, indicating a tissue-specific requirement for DUOX2 repression in liver metastasis (**Chart 3**).

8 Thus, we concluded that differential and decreased expression of DUOX2 defines the liver metastatic transcriptome in human cancer.

10 Discussion

11 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of DUOX2, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with liver metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer and breast cancer. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (12).

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Methods

We utilized GSE213402, GSE179979 and GSE124647 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer or breast cancer using RNA-sequencing data (public and published) and R-based computational methods.